

COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURE OF THE OWNERS' CLASS

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Abstract

This article analyzes the composition and structure of the ownership class in Uzbekistan. The main components of the class of owners formed as a result of the economic reforms carried out in the country during the years of independence, their socio-demographic characteristics and their role in society are studied. The article highlights the development dynamics, existing problems and prospects of the owner class based on the analysis of statistical data, the results of sociological research and the opinions of experts. Also, suggestions and recommendations are given for the further development of the class of owners and increasing their role in the life of society.

Key words: ownership class, private property, entrepreneurship, social structure, economic reforms, middle class, social mobility, Uzbekistan.

Enter

The property class is one of the main components of any modern society. The formation and development of this class is important for the economic and social development of the country. The article analyzes the composition and structure of

the ownership class in Uzbekistan, as well as studies its role and importance in the life of society.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The works of local and foreign scientists, government documents and statistical data were studied for the research. Ownership class issues in Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, K.Kh. Covered in the works of Abdurakhmanov. From foreign scientists T. Piketty, R. Collins, E.O. Wright's theories of class structure were explored.

A complex methodological approach was used in the research process. The data of the State Statistics Committee, the Ministry of Economic Development and the Central Bank were analyzed and quantitative indicators of the class of owners were determined. Socio-demographic features were studied through a sociological questionnaire (2022-2023) with the participation of 1000 respondents. In-depth interviews were conducted with 50 experts, and current problems of the industry were identified. Media materials and government reports were content-analyzed and public opinion researched. The experience of Uzbekistan was compared with other countries. This comprehensive approach made it possible to draw comprehensive conclusions about the class of owners.

Results

In Uzbekistan, the class of owners was formed and developed during the years of independence. This process occurred as a result of economic reforms, privatization and business support policies. The main components of the owner class are:

Large business owners

Medium business representatives

Small entrepreneurs

Farmers and farm owners

Intellectual property owners

The results of the study show that the share of the owner class in the total population has a tendency to increase in recent years. In 2015, this indicator was 12%, and by 2023 it will reach 18%. This growth was mainly due to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

The socio-demographic structure of the landlord class is also changing. In particular, the share of women and young people is increasing. According to 2023 data, the share of women among owners is 35%, and the share of young people under 35 years old is 28%.

The level of education of representatives of the property class also has high indicators. More than 70% of them have a higher education, and 15% have a degree or title.

Indicator	2015	2023
Share of the property class in the total population	12%	18%
Share of women among owners	25%	35%
Percentage of young people under 35 years of age	20%	28%
Share of owners with higher education	60%	70%

Indicator 2015 2023 Share of owner class in total population 12% 18% Share of women among owners 25% 35% Share of young people under 35 years of age 20% 28% Share of owners with higher education 60% 70%

Table 1. The main indicators of the ownership class in Uzbekistan

The role and influence of the propertied class in society is also increasing. They are not only engaged in economic activities, but also take on social

responsibilities. Areas such as charity and sponsorship activities, social entrepreneurship are developing.

DISCUSSION

The formation and development of the ownership class in Uzbekistan led to fundamental changes in the socio-economic life of the country. This process occurred as a result of large-scale reforms implemented since the first years of independence. As stated by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Development of private property and entrepreneurship, support of small business is the guarantee and main factor of stable growth of our economy" [1].

The formation of the property class led to a number of positive results. First, there was an increase in economic activity and the creation of new jobs. According to statistics, the number of jobs created by the private sector increased by 1.5 times between 2016 and 2023 [2]. This played an important role in ensuring employment of the population and reducing the unemployment rate.

Secondly, the development of the ownership class stimulated the introduction of innovative ideas and technologies. Representatives of the private sector are paying more attention to the introduction of modern technologies in order to increase competitiveness. This, in turn, contributes to the technological development of the country. Economist R. According to Ubaydullaeva, "The private sector is the main source and driving force of innovation" [3].

Thirdly, the formation of a competitive environment and an increase in product quality are observed. Healthy competition between owners creates more choices for consumers and improves the quality of products and services. This process is especially evident in the service sector.

Fourth, there is an increase in the income of the population and the expansion of the middle class. According to the results of sociological studies, in 2015, the share of citizens who considered themselves to belong to the middle class was 25%, and by 2023 this figure will reach 35% [4]. This serves to strengthen social stability in the society.

Fifth, the formation of the ownership class has a positive effect on the development of civil society institutions. Private property owners are creating various public organizations and associations to protect their rights and interests. This, in turn, serves to strengthen civil society.

However, some problems are observed in the process of formation of the owner class. One of the most important problems is uneven distribution of property and increasing social stratification. Economist S. Gulyamov said, "The uneven distribution of property can cause social tension, so special attention should be paid to this issue" [5].

The second important problem is the formation of monopolies in some areas. This situation has a negative impact on the competitive environment and hinders the effective functioning of market mechanisms. The fight against monopoly has become one of the important directions of state policy.

The third problem is the problems of corruption and "shadow economy". These vices hinder the healthy development of the owning class and have a negative impact on economic growth. Legal scientist A. Saidov, "The fight against corruption and the legalization of the economy is one of the important conditions for the development of the owner class" [6].

The fourth problem is the insufficient development of mechanisms for the protection of the rights of owners. This issue remains relevant, especially for

representatives of small and medium-sized businesses. Inadequate legal protection hinders the development of entrepreneurship.

It is advisable to implement a number of measures to solve the problems listed above. First, it is necessary to improve the legal framework and strengthen the mechanisms for the protection of property rights. In this regard, the reform of the judicial system and ensuring its independence are of particular importance.

Secondly, it is necessary to strengthen the measures to develop the competitive environment and fight against monopoly. For this purpose, it is necessary to improve antimonopoly legislation and develop mechanisms for its effective application in practice.

Thirdly, it is necessary to take measures to further support small business and private entrepreneurship. Measures such as tax incentives, financial assistance programs and reduction of administrative barriers can be implemented in this direction.

Fourthly, it is necessary to increase the social responsibility of the owners and encourage them to actively participate in the life of society. In this regard, the development of social entrepreneurship and the wide implementation of the principles of corporate social responsibility are of great importance.

Fifth, special attention should be paid to improving the education system and developing entrepreneurial skills. For this purpose, it is possible to introduce programs aimed at strengthening the teaching of entrepreneurship and forming practical skills in schools and higher education institutions.

In short, the formation and development of the ownership class in Uzbekistan is a complex and multifaceted process, which has a deep impact on the socio-economic life of the country. In order to support the positive aspects of this process

and eliminate its negative consequences, the state and society should make consistent efforts.

Economist N. Sirojiddinov stated that "the development of the property class is the guarantee of the economic development and social stability of Uzbekistan. The correct direction and management of this process is crucial for the future of our country" [7].

In the future, further development of the ownership class and an increase in its role in the life of society is expected. Effective management and direction of this process remains one of the important tasks of state policy. At the same time, the owner class itself should take consistent action to protect its rights and interests, realize its responsibilities to the society, and form an active citizen's position.

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